

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE VERBALIZERS OF THE CONCEPT OF “WEDDING” IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article touches upon the comparative analysis of the units that verbalize the concept of “wedding” in the English and Uzbek languages.

INTRODUCTION

From the beginning of the 21st century the researches based on the anthropocentric paradigm began to emerge in the Uzbek linguistics. These works were carried out mainly in the areas of sociolinguistics, cognitive linguistics, pragmatic linguistics, psycholinguistics and general theoretical issues of the anthropocentric paradigm. At the same time, the anthropocentric approach to language embodies the latest achievements in these areas and strengthens its status as an independent paradigm. Many researchers acknowledge that cognitive linguistics and linguoculturology are leading areas of the anthropocentric paradigm.

MAIN PART

Currently, in the researches on cognitive linguistics the issues of concept, its linguocognitive nature and verbalization in different languages are being actively discussed (Khoshimova N. A., 2021). For

instance, D. U. Ashurova interprets the concept as a logical, national phenomenon, saying that while the basis of this concept is the knowledge about studied subject or event, its expression is organized by the balance of linguistic means (lexical, phraseological, parameological, etc.) [D. U. Ashurova, 11]. Renowned linguist, Professor G. M. Hoshimov describes the concept as follows: “A concept is the result of not only two important processes, conceptualization and categorization, which are closely related to each other, but also it is an end result of a number of other important processes (such as psychologization, cognition, sociology, (linguo) semantization, sociolectization, stylization (like dialectization, variantization, and idiolectization), and it constitutes the cognitive basis of the linguistic semantics as a holistic conceptual/cognitive semantics”.

As a result of studying the abovementioned ideas, we can say that the concept is the

main result of several processes going on in our minds and it is a unit that requires in – depth study in cognitive linguistics (Kuchkarova Z., 2021). At this point, we want to focus on the concept of "wedding" in the English and Uzbek languages which are typologically non – related languages.

In particular, the "wedding" ceremony is a specific social reality that has its own description and definition in all nations – a unique event, which has a number of similarities and differences in the languages and cultures of different people. Some of their linguistic aspects have been analyzed in both the traditional linguistic direction and in the anthropocentric direction, in which important theoretical and practical conclusions have been drawn on the object of study (Mirzaev 1971; Juraboev 1971; Khusainova 1984; Kasimova 2018; Ashurova, Galieva 2018: 125 and others). In these researches, the ethnographic lexicon expressing the history, national-spiritual values, customs and traditions of the people of our country and English – speaking people has been studied to a certain extent. However, the verbal means expressing the concept of "wedding" in Uzbek and English have not been studied as separate objects of linguocognitive and linguoculturological analysis. In this article, we try to explore these aspects and make a comparative analysis and scientific coverage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on our comparative – typological analysis, we found that in the English and Uzbek languages, the concept of "wedding" is expressed in a systematic way through the following invariant types of language units: 1) morpheme; 2) lexeme; 3) syntaxemes: a) word combination, b)

sentence; 4) phraseological units; 5) texteme (discourseme). In the following, we will try to take each of these separately and analyze them based on empirical examples.

Thus, it is a universal law that the concept of "wedding" is expressed in languages through the following verbalizers:

a) By morphemes: In Uzbek: to'ychi, to'yparast, to'ybop, to'ychilik, to'ychiq, to'ylovchi, to'ygarchilik, to'yli, to'ylik, to'yboshi, to'yxat, to'yxona, to'y – tomosha, to'y – hasham, to'ybola. In English: wed, wedding, newlyweds, bridegroom, groomsman, braidsmaids, bride – to – be, pageboy, honeymoon.

b) By lexemes: 1) Simple lexemes: In Uzbek: to'y, bazm, marosim, ziyofat, nikoh, fотиha, kelin, kuyov, uylanmoq, nikohlanmoq, to'ylamoq, to'ybop, kuyovli and etc. In English: couple, bride, groom, ceremony, ring, confetti, bridal, nuptials, festivities and etc. 2) Compound lexemes: In Uzbek: to'y – hasham, kuyovnavkar, kuyovto'ra, yuzochdi, kelinsalom, kuyovchiqdi, kuyovqochdi etc. In English: groomsman, bridesmaids, pageboy, newlyweds, bridegroom etc.

c) By syntaxemes: 1) Word combinations: In Uzbek: to'y qilmoq, to'y bermoq, to'y boshlamoq, erga tegmoq, xotin olmoq, o'g'il to'yi, muchal to'yi, beshik to'yi, xatna to'yi, nikoh to'yi, oltin to'y, kumush to'y etc. In English: to get married, to officiate at a wedding, to perform a wedding, wedding dress, wedding gown, wedding reception, to tie the knot, Big Day, ruby wedding, wooden wedding, silver wedding, golden wedding, diamond wedding, wedding vows etc. 2) Sentences: In Uzbek: a) simple sentences: Qudachilik ming yilchilik; Nikoh o'qilish mobaynida onasi kuyov yelkasiga beqasam chopon

yopdi; To'yxona to'la to'ylovchi bo'ldi; b) compound sentences: Kuyovto'ra kelib qarab tursin, kim qanday sovg'a tashlaydi; Bu qish kuchim yetmaydi, kelasi qish katta to'y beraman etc. In English: a) simple sentences: A wedding is not a wedding without the feast; A wedding is the last gasp of your childhood family; Weddings are great places to meet people etc. b) compound sentences: We are a little crazy with wedding stuff, but I know we'd both love to catch up with you; Okay, well, that's obviously your dress for the wedding, and you have the perfect shoes for it, those gold ones you bought to wear with the gold sequined dress; If you can survive the wedding, they say, the rest is a piece of cake etc.

d) By phraseological and paramiological units: In Uzbek: to'y olmoq, qalin bermoq, non sindirmoq, bekami ko'st to'y, to'y bermoq, to'yni qizitmoq, to'yni buzmoq, to'yga intiq; To'y to'ydek bo'lsin; To'yga borsang to'yib bor; To'yning ovozasini karnayidan ma'lum; to'y kengash bilan bo'lur, o'lim - bemaslahat etc. In English: to pop the question, to hear the sound of wedding bells, to pair off, to marry into money, to alter one's condition, to please one's eye and plague one's heart; Always sample a maidens charms before the wedding; Wedlock is padlock; One for sorrow, two for mirth, three for wedding, four for birth; The wife cries before the wedding, the husband after; Three rings of marriage are the engagement ring, the wedding ring and the suffering etc.

e) By textemes: In Uzbek: Kuyov tarafdin fотиha to'y keldi. Fотиha to'yda qo'y, zig'ir moy, guruch, mayiz... bo'ldi. to'ylovchilar atagan sovg'a - salomlarini ro'molga tashladi. Birov bir kiyimlik atlas tashladi, birov shoyi tashladi. Ro'mol

deyarli to'ldi. duo esgu bo'ldi: - To'yniki to'yda qaytsin! In English: "I've been to ten weddings in the past three years," Alexa said. "I've been a bridesmaid in seven of those" etc.

The abovementioned examples and analysis show that the verbal means expressing the concept of "wedding" in the compared languages differ from other verbal means not only in their structural and semantic aspects, but also in their unique linguoculturological features. Each of the following examples also reflects the unique linguistic and cultural characteristics of a nation that has a language, for example, in English: "I've been to ten weddings in the past three years," Alexa said. "I've been a bridesmaid in seven of those"; In Uzbek: Kuyov tarafdin fотиha to'y keldi. Fотиha to'yda qo'y, zig'ir moy, guruch, mayiz... bo'ldi. to'ylovchilar atagan sovg'a - salomlarini ro'molga tashladi. Birov bir kiyimlik atlas tashladi, birov shoyi tashladi. Ro'mol deyarli to'ldi. duo esgu bo'ldi: - To'yniki to'yda qaytsin!

So, verbal means such as "weddings, bridesmaid" and "fотиha to'y", "Fотиha to'yda qo'y, zig'ir moy, guruch, mayiz... bo'ldi", "to'ylovchilar atagan sovg'a - salomlarini ro'molga tashladi", "To'yniki to'yda qaytsin" are syncretic language units that combine both denotative and connotative semantics, and can serve as obvious examples for linguocultures. Such linguocultures need to be paid special attention while learning languages and translating them from one language to another, otherwise from a linguodidactic and translational point of view, linguocultures can cause certain difficulties in learning a language or translating a text into a language.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above brief comparative analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

a) in the conceptosphere of the speakers of the English and Uzbek languages, the concept of "wedding" exists as a universal phenomenon, because this concept is one of the most important and necessary concepts from a communicative point of view, and it is impossible without its implementation in languages;

b) in languages, the verbal units expressing the concept of "wedding", i.e. verbalizers, are realized through almost all existing units of levels (except for phonemes);

c) some verbalizers of the concept of "wedding" can also serve as linguoculturemes and it is important to pay special attention to their linguocultural features in the teaching and translation processes and to study the specifics of languages and, where necessary, to fully reflect them in translation.

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